

Motivational training programme for oral hygiene of deaf children

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Abstract:

Introduction: The best line of protection against oral illnesses is regular oral hygiene. Its stringent behaviour is necessary to maintain dental health, especially for children with disabilities. The purpose of the study was to impart over time principles of appropriate dental care in to deaf children and evaluate over a period of a month.

Materials and methods: 40 children of aged between 6 to 12 years, who have acquired deafness are included in the study. A carefully created methodology that takes into account their limitations was employed for their training.

Results: A month training and follow up was done in terms of oral hygiene. Children with hearing impairments find it challenging to learn and adhere to oral care guidelines because

they have trouble communicating with the dental team. Use of the particular sign language was required.

Conclusion: In summary A genuine chance to enhance the oral environment and lower the risk of caries was presented by the specifically designed image teaching system and the oral hygiene training programme designed for children with hearing impairments.

Keywords: deaf children, oral hygiene, training programme, motivation, special, brushing

Introduction:

Good health is a fundamental right, a social goal and an essential human need. Oral health is a major determinant and an intrinsic part of general health. Children are prone to oral health problems when their oral hygiene maintenance is poor.¹

Every community has a group of disabled children who have little options for dental treatment, which raises their risk of oral illnesses.² Because of communication problems, they cannot get dental care, so their oral health is worse than that of typical children.³

From the standpoint of oral health, children who mostly need special care are considered to be at high risk. The dental health of these kids is not well enough documented.¹

Very less information is available regarding the dental hygiene and health literacy of the parents and special educators who are caring for these kids. According to reports, the most neglected health need of the disabled is dental care.⁴

In addition, it is extremely difficult for a deaf and mute child to approach the oral health care professional. Communication issues render inability of taking a complete history and outlining the treatment plan to these patients.⁵

Hence potential interventions to educate these children are essential regarding oral health. Various studies proved that oral hygiene instructions either direct or indirect are beneficial in normal children.⁶ But these special children require a conceptualised image system that displays the order of events, organising the phases of oral hygiene practices and a lot of perseverance and patience. Which can lead the child to cope with the standards for routine oral hygiene practice.²

So, the aim of the study was to undertake a motivational training programme in oral hygiene concepts in deaf children and evaluate it after a period of month.

Materials and methods:

40 children of aged between 6 to 12 years were included in the study. The training programme was conducted in Kalyan Deaf and Dumb school, Nagpur.

An organized and detailed plan was formulated for motivation and health education of children with hearing loss. The following tools were used to encourage and educate children with hearing loss about their health:

1. Demonstration tools: Plaster model teeth with and without carious destruction, red silicone showing plaque, and plaque-retentive places were demonstrated. Correct brushing technique was shown on the plaster cast.
2. Audio-visual materials: Cartoons videos, an animated short film showing importance of oral hygiene were used. Slide share showing parts of tooth, correct oral hygiene practices were shown as visual aids.
3. Motivational tools included a schedule that tracked each morning and evening brushing pattern, in addition to printed instructions for the kids and their parents was given. The Greene & Vermillion (Simplified - 1964) index was used to determine the state of oral hygiene, evaluating the presence of plaque on the buccal or labial (16, 11, 24, 31) and lingual (36, 46) surfaces of the permanent teeth that were present. If the primary teeth had not yet been penetrated by the permanent teeth, the plaque on their buccal surfaces-numbers 55, 51, 64, 81- and lingual surfaces- numbers 75 and 85-was assessed.⁷

The children with hearing loss were taught dental hygiene using a specific methodology that took into account their psychological makeup and physical impairments. The goal was to turn the practise of maintaining dental hygiene into a stereotype since they enjoy them.

Correctional and educational components: in order to practise good oral hygiene, children need to be equipped with the cognitive and practical skills. The "Tell, Show, Do" technique was modified into "Do as I do" model of imitation; and "step-by-step training in oral hygiene through specially crafted art system" was used.

Modern dental hygiene training programs was provided to parents together with additional motivating materials, written suggestions, and guidance on how to carry them out at home.

Results:

Statistical analysis was done by using descriptive and inferential statistics using Chisquare and software used the analysis were SPSS 27.0 version and GraphPad Prism 7.0 version and $p < 0.05$ is considered as level of significance.

According to Fig 1, 10% of poor OHI-S score no improvement. Whereas, 55% of fair score reduced to 40% and 35% good score improved to 50% to cases.

Table 1: A month training and follow up was done in terms of oral hygiene - Comparison of OHI score at pre and post training using Chi-square Test:

OHI Score	Pre-Training	Post Training	χ^2 -value
Poor	4(10%)	4(10%)	5.95 P≤0.05, NS
Fair	22(55%)	16(40%)	
Good	14(35%)	20(50%)	
Total	40(100%)	40(100%)	

Fig 1: Comparison of OHI score at pre and post training

Fig 2 shows comparison mean score of OHIS reduced post training to the deaf children. For processing of the obtained results paired t- test of Student was used. The following fig shows that the post training mean OHI-S score was comparatively reduced with improvement in oral hygiene status.

Fig 2:

Discussion:

In the present study, the higher plaque and calculus scores in oral hygiene index before motivation confirm poor oral hygiene status similar to earlier studies.⁸ Hence, the prime motive of this study was to instil appropriate oral health awareness in these children.

Education in general is one of the imperative factors responsible for behavioral change in children.⁹ In particular, oral health education is the key to preventing oral diseases. It is always healthier to educate school-age children because schools are the ideal setting to teach preventive dental health practices.¹⁰ and via them education can reach their families and community members as well.¹¹

One of the major effect of the disability in children with hearing loss is inadequate teaching and low motivation to practice oral hygiene.³ Thus, causing serious dental issues in these children. Communication difficulties cause questionable treatment modalities. These special children find it very difficult to acquire knowledge and cope up with abilities when only routine methods are used.^{1,3}

It takes special teachers and the efforts of the medical staff and parental assistance in order to resolve communication barriers.³ Training is required to change the behavior of children with impairments.^{12, 13} The situation of oral hygiene in children with hearing impairments is not well enough documented in the literature. Studies that show children with impairments have worse oral hygiene than those without them.² Reports show even worse results when hearing loss is combined with a mental condition.¹⁴ In these cases, the parents' socioeconomic status and degree of education are also negatively connected with their dental hygiene.² It is well established that early onset of the deficit significantly impairs the child's general development and brain maturation.¹⁵

Combining these problems, children with hearing loss frequently have bad oral health. The present study was conducted, that revealed children with hearing loss have poor dental hygiene. Jain M. et.al also confirmed similar findings.¹⁶ According, to Alsmark SS et al. this special group requires more time or explanations that are substituted by visual displays to teach oral hygiene.⁸ Significant reduction of plaque and calculus scores were observed in the indicating positive impact of visual motivation.

The childhood is the best stage for the formation of health habits.¹⁷ Teaching about oral health is the best approach to avoid oral problems. Numerous different instructional pedagogies have been covered, such as self-study resources, audio-visual aids, and (direct/indirect) and individual teaching. The results indicate that since visual instructions are so simple to follow and provide succinct, easily remembered information, they are more successful than textual instructions.¹⁸ The increased cognitive ability and the manner of learning and initiation in older age groups might have influenced the better outcome.

According to Flanders RA, the largest and most important group that may be reached by health education is found in the school system. Kids are not only learn fast and are eager to pick up new abilities, but they also run the danger of developing negative habits and

oral health issues. Therefore, it is crucial that school oral health teaching programs be developed further despite the contradictory nature of the research on their usefulness.¹⁷

Though it is necessary, health education by itself alone cannot address the issue. The educational and motivating process should be extended to the parents, carers, and teachers of special children. Customizing the treatment plan is a must when working with these special kids. Good oral hygiene levels could be better achieved with ongoing encouragement and reinforcement in the form of visual education along with longer follow up period.

Conclusion:

A particularly created picture training system and the developed oral hygiene training curriculum for children with hearing impairments present a real potential to improve the oral environment and reduce the prevalence of caries.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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